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Relationship Between Self-Esteem And Academic Achievement Among Public Secondary School Students In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among secondary school students in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the correlational research design. The area of the study was Anambra State. The population for the study consisted of 21,272 senior secondary school students in SS2 across 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. This included 9,550 male students and 11,722 female students. The sample of the study was 320 SS II students. The instrument for data collection was a standardized questionnaire by Rosenberg (1965). The instrument's reliability was established through a pilot test. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient values of 0.86. Pearson Product Moment Correlational Coefficient was used to analyse the research questions and hypotheses. The finding of the study revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among public secondary school students in Anambra State. Finding of the study revealed that the relationship between self-esteem and mathematics achievement is stronger among male secondary school students than female students. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended among others that Mathematics teachers in secondary schools should adopt instructional strategies that enhance students' confidence like step-by-step problem-solving approaches, interactive learning and personalised feedback. It was also recommended that schools should introduce targeted interventions such as mentorship programmes, female-led mathematics clubs and confidence-building workshops to bridge the gender gap in mathematics achievement.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Gender, Mathematics, Self-Esteem, Secondary Schools.

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is a direct representation of learning effectiveness and a reliable measure of the efficacy of the teaching and learning processes. Academic achievement refers to students' assessed achievement in tests in a specific study (Zheng, 2022). Academic achievement is defined by Gutiérrez and Tomás (2019) as a learner's achievement on teaching and learning evaluations, such as final examination scores, attained in school. Academic achievement describes academic outcomes that indicate the extent to which a student has achieved their learning goals. Nwanze et al. (2021) associated academic achievement with the percentage of marks obtained by students in their most recent examinations. Academic achievement in the context of this study can be defined as the measure of students' intellectual progress. Academic achievement has to do with what a learner is able to accomplish in the course of schooling. The realization of high academic achievement among secondary school students is dependent on students' self-esteem (Dawn, 2020). The assertion by Dawn

(2020) have not been empirically ascertained among students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study therefore seeks to determine empirically if self-esteem has any relationship with students' academic achievement.

Self-esteem is a fundamental aspect of human psychology that significantly influences an individual's growth, development, and overall well-being (Dawn, 2020). Self-esteem is a psychological need that motivates behaviour. It encompasses one's beliefs about themselves, which subsequently influence one's behaviours. These behaviours, in turn, contribute to shaping both their personal reality and the social dynamics of their communities. Self-esteem is the process by which individuals rate themselves, acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes to enable them participate effectively in the society (Mwangi et al., 2023). Self-esteem is understood as a psychological state, referring to individuals' perceptions and views of themselves (Ibrahim & Olatunji, 2017). It involves the process by which individuals assess themselves, acquire information, skills, and attitudes necessary for effective engagement in society (Kariuki et al., 2019). Rosenberg (as cited in Amos et al., 2016), maintained that self-esteem can be characterized as a favourable or unfavourable disposition towards oneself, while Harter in (Amos et al., 2016) defined self-esteem as the degree to which one appreciates, accepts, and respects oneself as an individual. Harter suggested two theoretical perspectives on self-esteem: one based on how individuals perceive success in specific domains and another stemming from their own self-perceptions. Ultimately, self-esteem represents a positive or negative assessment based on one's own attributes, encapsulating how individuals generally, feel about oneself. In the context of this study, self-esteem denotes the overall confidence individuals have in their worth and capabilities. On a broader scale, while there appears to be some connection between self-esteem and academic achievement across various studies, the consistency of this relationship seems to depend on various contextual factors like gender.

Gender is commonly believed to influence the development, expression, and display of self-esteem. Gender can be understood as a social and psychological differentiation between males and females, comprising a set of socially constructed behaviours and expectations within society (Nwabueze & Iremeka, 2018). It encompasses various aspects such as behaviours, attitudes, roles, and social statuses that are assigned to individuals based on their gender within a particular socio-cultural context. Gender is also perceived as culturally and socially constructed characteristics and roles that are attributed to individuals based on their biological and physical differences as male or female. Baker and Kelan (2019), maintain that gender is a psycho-social concept used to examine the roles, responsibilities, opportunities, and needs of individuals within society. This includes economic, social, and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being male or female.

It has been shown that gender distinctions can influence the formation and development of students' self-esteem in academics (Postigo et al., 2022). The stronger the gender stereotypes within educational environments, the more significant the gender-mediated impacts on academic self-esteem (Koivuhovi et al., 2019). Gender imbalances in academic self-esteem often align closely with gender stereotypes (Ertl et al., 2017). Simply put, male students who maintain a higher sense of self-esteem in mathematics tend to perform better in the subject. Conversely, female students with positive self-esteem in verbal skills are more likely to excel in languages (Espinoza & Taut, 2020). Furthermore, concerning self-esteem, there are more pronounced gender differences among gifted students compared to those with average abilities (Preckel et al. cited in Espinoza & Taut, 2020).

Several reviews have investigated the gender-mediated effects of academic self-esteem on educational constructs. Gender has been found to moderate social comparison in the classroom, negatively impacting female students' expectations of success and self-esteem (Postigo et al., 2022). Gender stereotypes can also negatively affect female students' self-esteem in mathematics and science, leading to their underrepresentation in academic competitions (Steeh et al., 2019). Girls with lower self-esteem tend to experience higher levels of math anxiety compared to boys (Kaur et al., 2022). The composition of the class can also affect female students' academic self-esteem, with single-sex classes proving beneficial for their self-esteem in science-related subjects (Belfi et al. in Kaur et al., 2022).

In Anambra State, there is a troubling trend of decreasing academic achievement among secondary school students in internal examinations, reflecting broader challenges observed nationwide. The difficulties faced by students in subjects like Mathematics in both internal and external examinations in Anambra State seem to show a fluctuation in students' academic achievement. Mathematics is one of the most essential subjects in secondary school, which justifies its compulsory status in the Nigerian education system as mandated by the Federal Government. The FRN (2013) stated that mathematics plays a crucial role in instilling the right values and attitudes necessary for individual survival and national development. It provides students with the fundamental mathematical background required for higher education, equips them with essential skills, abilities, and competencies—both mental and physical—that enable them to contribute effectively to societal progress.

Despite these objectives and the overall significance of mathematics, students' academic achievement in the subject seem to be on a decline over the past decade. Okpe et al. (2022) noted that this trend is evident in both internal and external examinations, particularly in assessments conducted by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO). Statistics on the percentage of students that obtained credit in five subjects including Mathematics validates this assertion. Although, the trend shows some improvement, there are fluctuations in students' achievement in Mathematics is still below expectation both at national and state levels. Anambra State, for example, is not at par with her counterpart states such as Abia and Imo. With 70.0% and 73.0% of students in Anambra State obtaining 5 credits including Mathematics in 2019 and 2020 fell below 87.2 and 82.6% obtained in Abia and Imo states respectively in Mathematics respectively. However, it recorded improvement in 2021 WAEC examination with 91.2% of her students obtaining 5 credits in five subjects including Mathematics compared to Abia's 79.5% and Imo's 81.7%, and states in the south-east (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). The researcher wonders if these could be associated with the students' self-esteem. Omeodu (2021) found that students with positive self-esteem tend to excel academically when provided with supportive learning environments. However, the study did not put into consideration the moderating role of gender on self-esteem and students' academic achievement in Anambra State. It is against this background that the researcher intends to investigate the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Academic achievement, particularly in Mathematics, serves as a critical measure of educational success at the secondary school level. In Anambra State, students' performance in internal and external examinations such as those conducted by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO) reflects growing concern over their mathematical competencies. Although Anambra State has recorded commendable academic outcomes in some years, students' performance in Mathematics has continued to show a pattern of inconsistency and fluctuation. This trend raises questions about the effectiveness of current teaching and learning strategies for Mathematics across public secondary schools in the state. Despite various interventions by the government and educational stakeholders aimed at improving Mathematics education, the academic achievement of students in this core subject remains below expectations. Comparative statistics show that Anambra State often trails behind peer states such as Abia and Imo in Mathematics performance, highlighting a regional disparity that warrants further investigation. Observations from classroom settings and informal discussions with students reveal persistent challenges related to comprehension, problem-solving skills, and sustained interest in Mathematics. Research in educational psychology suggests that such academic outcomes may be influenced by individual and environmental factors, including self-esteem. While existing studies have found both positive and inconsistent associations between self-esteem and academic achievement, the precise nature of this relationship—especially in Mathematics—remains unclear. Adding to this complexity is the potential moderating role of gender. Gender norms and societal expectations often influence students' self-perception and attitudes toward specific academic domains. For instance, Mathematics is frequently stereotyped as a male-dominated field, which may affect girls' confidence and performance, while reinforcing boys' alignment with the subject. Evidence suggests that boys and girls

develop and express self-esteem differently, with possible implications for how they perform academically in Mathematics. However, within the context of public secondary schools in Anambra State, limited empirical research has explored the intersection of self-esteem, gender, and academic achievement in Mathematics. Most existing studies either generalize findings across subjects or lack localized data that reflect the unique socio-educational dynamics of the state. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by investigating the relationship between self-esteem and students' academic achievement in Mathematics, while also examining whether gender moderates this relationship among public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among secondary school students in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among public secondary school students in Anambra State.
2. determine the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among public secondary school students in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female public secondary school students in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among public secondary school students in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female public secondary school students in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design. This design was appropriate as it focused on the strength and direction of relationships between variables without implying causality. Anambra State was chosen for its strong educational reputation, though recent declines in mathematics performance raised concerns about psychological factors such as self-esteem. The study population comprised 21,272 SS2 students in 267 public secondary schools, with a sample of 320 students selected through a multistage sampling procedure involving random, stratified, and cluster sampling across four schools in Awka and Aguata education zones. SS2 students were targeted because they were not engaged in external exams and possessed sufficient academic maturity. Data were collected using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale and students' mathematics achievement scores obtained from the Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Awka. The Rosenberg instrument was face and construct validated by experts in educational psychology and measurement, and subjected to Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.786 and a significant Bartlett's test result confirmed the data's suitability for PCA, affirming the instrument's construct validity. A pilot study in Enugu State confirmed the reliability of the instrument, yielding a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.86. Data were collected in person by the researcher and assistants using an on-the-spot method, yielding a 95% response rate (305 out of 320 questionnaires returned). Data analysis was conducted using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient to address the research questions, and the significance of relationships was tested at the 0.05 level using SPSS version 26.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among public secondary school students in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Pearson R Analysis Showing the Relationship between Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement in Mathematics among Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Source of Variation		Self-Esteem	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Remark
Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.568	Moderate positive relationship
	N	305	305	
Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	.568	1	
	N	305	305	

Findings in Table 1 revealed a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .568$) which indicates a moderate positive relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in mathematics. The findings suggest that self-esteem is an important factor influencing students' achievement in mathematics.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female public secondary school students in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Pearson R on Relationship between Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement in Mathematics among Male and Female Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Gender			Self-Esteem	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Remark
Male	Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.671	High positive relationship
		N	125	125	
	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	.671	1	
		N	125	125	
Female	Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.279	Moderate positive relationship
		N	180	180	
	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	.279	1	
		N	180	180	

Findings in Table 2 revealed a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .671$) for male public secondary school students, indicating a high positive relationship between self-esteem and mathematics achievement. The findings further revealed a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .279$) for female public secondary school students, indicating a moderate positive relationship between self-esteem and mathematics achievement. However, the relationship between self-esteem and mathematics achievement is stronger among male students ($r = .671$) than female students ($r = .279$).

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State.

Table 3: Pearson r Test of Significance of relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State.

Source of Variation	N	Self-Esteem r	Academic Achievement in Eng. Lang. r	P-value	Remark
Self-Esteem	305	1	0.568	0.000	Significant
Academic Achievement in Eng. Lang.	305	0.568	1		

Findings in Table 3 revealed a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.568$) and p -value = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Since the relationship is significant, the null hypothesis that “the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State is not significant” is rejected. Thus, the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State is significant.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Table 4: Pearson r Test of Significance of relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Gender			Self-Esteem	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Remark
Male	Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.671**	
		P-value		0.000	Significant
		N	125	125	
	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	.671**	1	
		P-value	.000		
		N	125	125	
Female	Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.279**	
		P-value		.000	Significant
		N	180	180	
	Academic Achievement in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	.279**	1	
		P-value	.000		
		N	180	180	

Findings in Table 4 revealed Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .671$, $p = 0.000$) for male secondary school students and Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .279$, $p = 0.000$) for female secondary school students. Both relationships are statistically significant, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis that the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State is not significant.

DISCUSSION

The study found a moderate positive relationship ($r = .568$) between self-esteem and academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State. One possible reason for

this finding is that self-esteem influences students' perception of their ability to solve mathematical problems. Students with higher self-esteem tend to approach mathematics with confidence, leading to greater persistence, problem-solving skills, and overall academic achievement. Conversely, students with low self-esteem may develop anxiety or negative attitudes toward mathematics, which could hinder their ability to perform well in the subject. This finding is supported Okenyi et al. (2024) who revealed that self-esteem has a significant positive relationship with pupils' academic achievement in mathematics. In the same vein, Amos et al. (2016) reported a significant positive relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among undergraduate students.

Furthermore, finding of the study revealed that the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State is significant. The significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State suggests that students who believe in their abilities are more likely to engage actively in learning, persist in solving complex problems, and maintain a positive outlook toward mathematics. High self-esteem fosters resilience, enabling students to overcome challenges and approach mathematical tasks with determination. In contrast, students with low self-esteem may develop anxiety or avoidance behaviours, leading to reduced participation and lower academic achievement in mathematics. This finding is consistent Yidani and Arthur (2024) who found a statistically significant positive influence of students' self-esteem on their academic engagement. Yidani and Arthur (2024) further asserted that self-esteem positively influenced cognitive, affective, and behavioural engagement all of which are crucial for success in mathematics. Similarly, Gebresilase and Zhao (2023) established that student-teacher interaction had a significant impact on both self-esteem and academic achievement. Gebresilase and Zhao (2023) further revealed that self-esteem played a mediating role in the relationship between student-teacher interaction and academic achievement, suggesting that fostering supportive learning environments could enhance students' self-esteem and improve their academic performance in mathematics.

The findings of the study revealed a high positive relationship between self-esteem and Mathematics achievement among male secondary school students ($r = .671$), while a moderate positive relationship was observed among female students ($r = .279$). This stronger correlation among male students suggests that self-esteem has a more pronounced influence on their academic success in Mathematics compared to their female counterparts. One possible reason for this is that societal and cultural norms often encourage boys to be more confident and assertive in subjects like Mathematics, which is traditionally perceived as a male-dominated field. As a result, male students with higher self-esteem may be more willing to take risks, actively engage in problem-solving, and persist through academic challenges. In contrast, female students' achievement in Mathematics may be influenced by a combination of self-esteem and other factors, such as study habits, teacher support, and societal expectations regarding gender roles in education. This finding aligns with Arshad et al. (2015) who revealed that male students generally exhibited higher self-esteem than their female counterparts, and their academic achievement in Mathematics was significantly influenced by their confidence levels. Arshad et al. (2015) also found that while female students performed well academically, self-esteem did not have as strong a direct impact on their Mathematics achievement as it did for male students. Munamu (2016) reported that male students tend to have higher self-esteem in academic settings compared to female students, and this confidence positively influenced their engagement and success in subjects that require logical reasoning and problem-solving in Mathematics.

The finding of the study revealed that the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State is significant. The finding that the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State is significant aligns with previous research that has explored the link between self-perception and academic success. Studies have consistently shown that self-esteem plays a crucial role in students' motivation, engagement, and overall academic performance across various subjects, including Mathematics. The finding is in consonance with Arshad et al. (2015)

who found a significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among secondary school students, with male students generally exhibiting higher self-esteem levels. In the same vein, Munamu (2016) reported that self-esteem significantly influenced students' academic achievement, particularly in subjects requiring analytical and problem-solving skills, such as Mathematics.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that there is significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra State. The findings indicate that while self-esteem positively correlates with academic achievement, the strength of this relationship varies based on gender and subject area. Male students exhibited a stronger correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement in Mathematics compared to their female counterparts. This suggests that self-perception plays an important role in students' learning outcomes in Mathematics that require confidence and persistence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffers the following recommendations:

1. Mathematics teachers in secondary schools should adopt instructional strategies that enhance students' confidence, such as step-by-step problem-solving approaches, interactive learning and personalised feedback. This will help strengthen the link between self-esteem and academic achievement in mathematics.
2. Given the stronger relationship between self-esteem and mathematics achievement among male students, efforts should be made to provide additional support for female students. Schools should introduce targeted interventions such as mentorship programmes, female-led mathematics clubs and confidence-building workshops to bridge the gender gap in mathematics achievement.

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